

Assessing Factors Affecting Budgeting In Ghana: Evidence from Municipal, Metropolitan and District Assemblies

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Abstract

the agitations of citizens of poor developmental programs of District Assemblies failure of budget preparation and implementation. This has warranted the need to identify the various factors and challenges affecting district Assemblies budget. We assessed the factors affecting budget preparation and challenges affecting budget implementation of local assemblies in Ghana. The sample comprises 140 respondents from selected municipal, metropolitan and district assemblies in Ghana. We analyzed the data obtained through statistical package for social science (SPSS) with the use of structured questionnaires. We find negative relationship between budget preparation and the factor variables. This means that, all the factor variables (delays in submission of inputs from other departments, inadequate funds to carry out the exercise unrealistic demands from department, outdated revenue data, difficulty in budget preparation) are negatively related to budget preparation of MMDAs in Ghana. Interestingly, the effect is significant. We find a statistical significant negative effect of budget implementation and the challenging factors. Additional analyses supports the findings obtained

Keywords: Budget, Internal Generated Fund, Common fund, District Assembly, Ghana.

Introduction

Ghana has implemented comprehensive local government and decentralization reforms as an alternative development strategy (MLGRD, 2010). The programmed has operated on four main, interrelated pillars, namely political decentralization, administrative decentralization, decentralized planning and fiscal decentralization. Over the years a fifth piece, public-private partnerships, has assumed increasing importance (MLGRD, 2010). The implementations of the decentralization system have brought about some successes including the creation of two hundred and sixteen (216) Metropolitan, Municipal and District Assemblies (MMDAs), the transfer of authority, resources and responsibilities from the center to the local level, awareness-raising amongst the citizenry, infrastructural development with support from the District Assemblies Common Fund and increased collaboration between localities and development partners. Nevertheless, basic issues need to be addressed. Experiences from implementation have included incoherence or even contradictions in sectorial approaches to decentralization; the need to clarify the role of the region in the national governance architecture; the persisting slowness in integrating decentralized departments into the assembly administration and in implementing fiscal decentralization; the ineffectiveness of local government sub-structures; low capacities and motivation of assembly members; the need to stimulate popular participation in local governance; and streamlining relationships with traditional authorities. (MLGRD, 2010).

The focus and content of local financial management practices of local government units of government in developing countries have become a major national and international concern. This is because local government units are expected to champion development interventions in their respective jurisdictions. As the years go by, societal needs and aspirations keeps on increasing and changing which need to be merged with government budgetary preparations and implementations. The quest of the central government to transform the livelihood of all citizens in the country warranted the adoption of decentralization system in 1978. This was to transfer power and resources to the grass root level so that development will be at their door step.

Finance is the 'lifeblood' of decentralization. However, it has remained a major problem for decentralization in Ghana (Ayee, 2006). In practical terms, Prud'homme (1989) argues that subnational governments generate

about 20% of total government revenues while they spend about 30%. The difference of 10% is made up of Central Government transfers. Thus, revenues to local governments consist of internally-generated revenues and Central Government transfers. The 1992 Constitution requires that 7.5% of the total revenue of Ghana be transferred to local governments based on an annually agreed formula by the legislature. The Internally Generated Funds (IGFs) include rates and fees, rents, fines and licenses, investments and income from commercial activities. However, local governments in Ghana still rely heavily on Central Government transfers mainly because of capacity challenges in internal revenue mobilization, mismanagement and corruption. (Nana Nimo, 2013).

Although the creation of the DACF and the payment of funds into the Fund is a constitutional requirement, there have been instances where payments into the Fund have delayed for more than one year, resulting in the failure to disburse monies to the Metropolitan, Municipal and District Assemblies (MMDAs). Also, there have been complaints from the general public and reports of alleged misapplication and financial malpractices in connection with the disbursement and use of the proceeds of the Central Government's grants to the MMDAs. (Nana Nimo, 2013). Before the 1998 Local government reforms, District Assemblies in Ghana were mandated to plan and prepare their budgets and generate enough funds to finance their local infrastructure developments programs. However, colossal challenges has accounted for this fiscal responsibility to meet this reforms.

The implementation of the MMDAs composite budget has faced several problems that have in turn affected the performance of the District Assemblies. It has become common knowledge that the budgetary allocation of resources to various sectors of the public sector and especially at the local authority level is not a good indicator of the quality and quantity of goods and services delivered by these sectors. This is especially the case in countries where central government agencies are very reluctant to relinquish their power over local authorities and transfer resources to them. In Ghana, where corruption and political interference in the activities of the local authorities are alleged to be very high, resources meant for these authorities may never reach them or where they are received, the use of the resources could be subject to a lot of abuse. There is the problem of the failure and refusal of some MMDAs to follow the guidelines for the use of the Fund, so it is significant to examine distinct facets to ensure effective preparation and implementation of budgets of MMDAs in Ghana. Therefore, we sought to examine the factors and challenges engulfed MMDAs of Ghana in preparation and implementation of budget.

Our study contributes to the literature of budgeting and performance in diverse ways. First, we examined a non-heterogeneous sample. Most literature used one district assembly in assessing the factors that could affect MMDAs budget preparation and implementation. Nonetheless, MMDAs in Ghana has been expanded, but numerous factors and challenges affecting their composite budget preparation and implementation have been overlooked. Second, even though, few studies has examined on this same subject but none examined the challenges faced by MMDAs of budget implementation. Therefore, research scholars believed that, assessing the challenges and factors affecting budgeting of MMDAs would be significant.

We believed the results of our study would be paramount to the government, budget analyst, coordinating directors, citizens of communities, and all stakeholders on the proof of the importance of budgeting on the performance of municipal, metropolitan and district Assemblies.

The rest of the manuscript is as follows: The next section address the Brief literature, section three talks about the data and methods of the study. It follows by the results and findings, the last section addresses the summary, conclusions and provides policy recommendations

Related Literature Review

The history of decentralization in Ghana is traced back by Aye (2000) to the introduction of indirect rule by the British colonial authorities in 1878, lasting until 1951. During this period the colonial administration ruled indirectly through the native political institution (i.e. the chiefs), by constituting the chief and elders in a given

district as the local authority, with powers “to establish treasuries, appoint staff and perform local government functions” (Nkrumah, 2000). Nkrumah also makes the interesting observation that, under indirect rule, downward accountability of chiefs to the people was replaced by upward accountability to the colonial authorities: “the democratic ideals underlying chieftaincy in Ghana, which made chiefs accountable to their peoples, began to suffer as the recognition by the central government was more crucial to the chief than the support of his people” (ibid.). Thus, there are some echoes here, as well as obvious differences, with relations in the contemporary period between central and local government in Ghana, dispelling any lingering notions of a necessary association between decentralization and democracy, and confirming how decentralization can be used as a political mechanism by ruling political elites to reinforce their control.

In the post-independence period from 1957 onwards, local government was generally weak and subject to the centralization of power that was typical of the post-colonial state in Africa (Tordoff, 1994; Nkrumah, 2000).

A historical aspect was the decentralization reforms introduced in the early period of Rawlings’ populist military rule (1981-92). In 1983, Rawlings’ PNDC government announced a policy of administrative decentralization of central government ministries, alongside the creation of People’s Defense Committees (PDCs) in each town and village. The PDCs, made up of local PNDC activists as self-identified defenders of the ‘revolution’, effectively took over local government responsibilities, though often limited to mobilizing the implementation of local self-help projects (Nkrumah, 2000), while the de-concentrated ministries played a more significant role. Ayee (2000) notes that despite the PNDC’s populist rhetoric, its interest in decentralization reflected that of previous regimes, that is, an interest in the administrative decentralization of central government and not the devolution of political authority to the local level.

The Republic of Ghana is now a unitary state with multiparty democracy as provided by the Constitution of the Republic of Ghana, 1992, which established the Fourth Republic. The 1992 Constitution marked the end of the rule of the Provisional National Defense Council (PNDC), and a return to multiparty democracy in Ghana. (CLGF, 2013). Since gaining independence in 1957, as the first country in colonial Africa to become independent, successive governments in Ghana have looked to a vibrant local government system to aid the country’s development. Attempts at decentralization were introduced, for instance, in 1983 under Rawlings’ military rule (Crawford, 2004). Ghana’s current program of decentralization was initiated in 1988 (ibid). The process of decentralization continued and was endorsed by Ghana’s first multiparty government that came into power in 1992.

Purpose of decentralization in Ghana

Many countries that enjoy superb order, stability, and experience continuous success in this world have long time ago embarked on decentralization (Ayim-Aboagye, 2013). This principle, which we heard of it many thousands of years ago even among the Israelites of biblical antiquity, has blessed those nations that saw to it that they implement among its citizens. According to Ayim-Aboagye (2013), “*in order to avoid the use of force or coercion in the civilized Ghana to change things or threaten the peace of others, decentralization must be adopted to give this country the peace and stability it deserves in its young democracy*”.

The purpose of decentralization in Ghana was to help distribute power away from the central government to local branches or governments. It was aimed to facilitate delegation of decision-making to the subunits of an organization. It was realized that as the decisions are made in the lower level, decentralization becomes greater and as decisions are made by those who have the most knowledge about local conditions the outcome becomes impressive. These according to Ayim-Aboagye (2013) underlined the introduction of decentralization in Ghana.

The introduction of decentralization has the potential to guarantee these four major advantages, (Ayim-Aboagye, 2013); Firstly, those districts, municipalities, and metropolitan officers/politicians that are more serious and know how to utilize their own resources allocated to them by the Central Government, will be able

to develop their districts or regions very well. It leads to healthy competition, which encourage all districts, municipalities, and metropolitans to strive for better developments. Secondly, the political arena will receive some orderliness, peace, and stability, as future politicians will be selected from among these experienced districts, municipalities, and metropolitan government politicians. It will be very hard for any novice to decide to run for political position and succeeds, as people will be looking for his credentials, whether he has had any political appointments before or not. Because the nation has these governments that have been imbued with power and authority, the central government will be relieved from some of these petty problems that could allow the people to blame the ruling government, which could shift their important focus. The President will be more concerned with foreign policies and the overall major developments in the country, such as industrialization and infrastructure.

Thirdly, the use of force or coercion to change things or influence decisions will not be seen because there will be more education concerning who will be a good president. This is because those who want to be elected as Presidents will have to prove to the nation and the electorates that they had accomplished something in their political careers, when they were either functioning in the local government, that is, district, municipalities, and metropolitan or other distinguished public services in the country. These areas will prepare all politicians for parliament and other major political appointments, which exist in the country and abroad.

Now, since the President is going to be compelled to work with only those politicians that have been given mandate by the citizens to be in parliament, it will prevent favoritism and abolish away a government that becomes concerned with people from one specific tribal group.

Lastly, with decentralization becoming a reality, then the best politicians in the country are not going to come from parliament or foreign ministries, but the districts, municipalities, and the metropolitan regions. These men earn the higher incomes in the country, together with the CEOs, because they do the real politics of management and care-taking of government businesses.

Those other politicians in the country are also respected but these local government officials receive more respect, because they do the real business of governing the people.

The 1992 Constitution, which marked the transition to multi-party democracy at the national level, endorsed the 1988 reforms. It consolidated the aim of decentralization within the overall context of a liberal democratic constitution, yet essential democratic elements remained compromised, especially through the retention of presidential appointments and non-partisan local elections. The objective of decentralization was laid out unambiguously in Chapter 20, entitled ‘Decentralization and Local Government’.

This states emphatically that: “Local government and administration shall be decentralized” (Article 240 [1]), and that the “functions, powers, responsibilities and resources should be transferred from the Central Government to local government units” (Article 240 [2]). The autonomous role of local government, with discretionary powers at the local level, was inferred by the provision that: “measures should be taken [by Parliament] to enhance the capacity of local government authorities to plan, initiate, co-ordinate, manage and execute policies in respect of matters affecting local people” (Article 240[2][b]). The principles of participation in local government and downward accountability to the populace was emphasized by the statement that: “To ensure the accountability of local government authorities, people in particular local government areas shall, as far as practicable, be afforded the opportunity to participate effectively in their governance” Article 240[2][e]. Indeed, the democratic intent in the decentralization provisions is made explicit in another section of the Constitution which states that the: “State shall take appropriate measures *to make democracy a reality* by decentralizing the administrative and financial machinery of government to the regions and districts and by affording all possible opportunities to the people to participate in decision-making at every level of national life and in government” (Article 35[6][d]) (emphasis added). This is somewhat contradicted, however, by the retention from the PNDC 1988 reforms of non-partisan local elections and presidential powers of appointment. Thus, District Assemblies are composed of 70 per cent elected members, with candidates standing as

individuals and political parties banned, and 30 per cent of members appointed by the President, formally “in consultation with traditional authorities and other interest groups in the district” (Article 242[d]). Additionally, the appointment of the District Chief Executive (DCE) by the President was retained, though with the approval needed of two thirds of District Assembly members (Article 243[1]). The DCE is the political head of the local executive, centrally involved in decision-making, with a District Co-coordinating Director (DCD) as the highest ranking civil servant.

As regards the financing of local government, the Constitution makes clear that the DAs “should have sound financial bases with adequate and reliable sources of revenue” [Article 240(2)], with an attempt to secure this through the establishment of the District Assembly Common Fund (DACF). This is determined annually by Parliament, but with allocations “not less than five per cent of the total revenues of Ghana” [Article 252(2)]. The proceeds of the DACF are then allocated between DAs on the basis of a revenue sharing formula approved by Parliament.

Legal Framework for MMDAs’ Budgeting in Ghana

Ghana’s Public Financial Management (PFM) system is based on a good legal and regulatory framework which sets out appropriate budget and accountability structures and is backed by the 1992 Constitution and other Acts of Parliament. (MOF, 2012)

The budget cycle in the MMDAs is guided by Local Government Act 1993 (Act 462), National Development Planning Systems Act 1994 (Act 455), DACF Act 1993 (Act 455) and Audit Service Act 2000. In addition, the Financial Administration Act (FAA) Act 2003 (Act 654) and Financial Administration Regulations (FAR), 2004, Public Procurement Act, 2003 (Act 663) Local Government Service Act, 2003 (Act 656) Internal Audit Agency Act, 2003 (Act 658), Financial memorandum, 2008, Regulations, 2004 (LI 1802) Decentralization Policy & Framework reviewed in 2010 and lastly L.I 1961, 2009. These laws mandate the assemblies as Planning, budgeting and rating authority. (MOF, 2012)

- Section 92 (3) of the local Government Act (Act 462) envisages the implementation of the composite budget system under which the budgets of the departments of the District Assemblies would be integrated into the budgets of the District Assemblies

In Ghana, the term ‘Composite Budget’ means an aggregation of projected revenues and expenditures of the Departments and institutions of the MMDAs. It is defined under Section 92 (3) of the Local Government Act of 1993 as: *‘The budget for a district shall include the aggregate revenue and expenditure of all departments and organisations under the District Assembly and the District Co-ordinating Directorate, including the annual development plans and programmes of the departments and organisations under the Assembly.’*

Composite budgeting is a tool to effectively facilitate, the coordination, harmonization of planning and budgeting at the district level. (MOF, 2012)

The Composite Budget of MMDAs

The District Composite Budgeting system is expected to achieve the following amongst others:

- Ensure that public funds follow functions to give meaning to the transfer of staff transfer from the Civil Service to the Local Government Service;
- Establish an effective integrated budgeting system which supports intended goals, expectation and performance of government at the local level;
- Deepen the uniform approach to planning, budgeting, financial reporting and auditing
- Facilitate harmonized development and introduce fiscal prudence in the management of public funds at the MMDA level.

In 2012 Government directed all Metropolitan Municipal and District Assemblies (MMDAs) to prepare the composite budget which integrates departments under Schedule one of the Local Government Integration of Department Act LI 1961 (MOF, 2012). This policy initiative will upscale full implementation of fiscal decentralization and ensure that the utilization of all public resources at the local level takes place in an efficient, effective, transparent and accountable manner for improved service delivery.

The Composite Budgeting process of MMDAs

The District Medium Term Development Planning process and the MTEF Strategic Planning Process which is the basis for formulating the Budgets of central government line Ministries and Department go through similar processes. Medium Term Development Plans of assemblies should therefore be used as a basis for formulating the district composite budgets in line with the MTEF framework. For this reason, the DMTDP and AAPs should serve as the foundation for the preparation of the composite budgets.

The goal of the Composite Budget is to ensure that the policies and programs of the Assembly are implemented in an integrated manner using the budget as the tool. Each stage therefore in the budget process has a role in helping to develop and implement the policies of the MMDA and integrating local priorities aligned to the national policies.

Conceptual Framework

We conceptualize the relationship between independent factors affecting budget preparation and the challenges affecting budget implementation. Therefore, the conceptualization of our study with relevant variables are developed to answer the research questions. Budget preparation (BP), Budget implementation (BI), budget preparation factors, and budget implementation factors. Budget preparation are been affected by the (delays in submission of inputs, inadequate funds, unrealistic demands from departments, outdated revenue data, and difficulty in budget preparation input) which integrates leading to (insufficient IGF, DACF, unrealistic and outdated socio economic data, failure to prosecute defaulters, and poor performance of revenue collectors) which affect districts budget implementation. They are captured below,

Based on the literature reviewed, and theoretical framework, we formulated the following hypothesis:

H1a. Delay of input submission negatively affects budget preparation

H1b. inadequate funds negatively affects MMDs budget preparation

H1c. There is significantly negative effects of outdated revenue on budget preparation

H2.a. Less IGF significantly and negatively affects budget implementation of MMDs

H2b. Less DACF has a significant negative effects on MMDs budget implementation

H2c. Unrealistic socio-economic data has a significant negative effects on MMDs budget implementation

H2d. Poor revenue collection negatively affects MMDs budget implementation in Ghana

Data and Methods

We employed descriptive form of research to examine the relationship between study variables. Then we conducted a survey to aid in the data collection from the sailed respondents. We used questionnaires which was prepared, pre-tested and reviewed. However, for the inclusion of the sample, the following restrictions were imposed, only sampled district assemblies are selected. Municipal district assemblies with less Assembly members and other missing relevant data were excluded from the study. We used purposively sampling method in selecting the targeted respondent from the sampled Municipal Metropolitan District Assembly. We selected all district coordinating directors, chief finance officers, budget analyst, internal auditors, revenue superintend and all assembly members of the selected MMDAs.

Questionnaires

We conducted a pilot and pretesting of the questionnaire by deploying it to various budget analyst, Chief Finance Officers, coordinating directors, auditors, and assembly members from the selected metropolitan, municipal and district assemblies (MMDs) in Ghana. The questionnaires were given to experts from the Ministry of Finance, and expert in governance and administration known by the authors. They were asked to review, correct and endorse for improvements and amendments of the original draft work of the questionnaire for its implication, content as well as the wordings. The selected MMDAs are displayed in appendix. The revised and modified questionnaires were deployed to the targeted respondents. The questionnaires were into folds. The first fold asked the respondents profile. The remaining section addressed and asked questions on factors affecting budget preparation-of MMDAs in Ghana, and the challenges affecting budget implementation of MMDAs in Ghana. We included a cover letter stating the aims of our study, defined budgeting, the factors and challenges affecting it preparation and implementation and the confidentiality of the responses were assured, hence increase the response rate.

Model Specification

To examine the factors affecting budget preparation of district assemblies in Ghana, we estimate regressions of factors influences budget preparation. This Eq. (1) using multiple regressions as follows

$$BP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 DeIM_1 + \beta_2 IFDs_2 + \beta_3 ODRDT_3 + \beta_4 DFTY_4 + \varepsilon_{it} \quad \text{Eq.1}$$

Where BP is the budget preparation which is which will measured by respondents rating the effects of this on budget preparation, DeIM is delays in submission of inputs from other departments, IFDs is inadequate funds to carry out the exercise unrealistic demands from department, ODRDT, is-outdated revenue data, DFTY is difficulty in budget preparation, β_0 Indicate the constant parameter of the regression model. ($\beta_1 - \beta_4$) represent the coefficients of the independent variables on the dependent variable and ε_{it} is the stochastic or error term.

To examine the challenges or the factors influencing the budget implementation of MMDAs in Ghana, We estimate a series of Eq. (2) Using multiple regressions as follows,

$$BI = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IGF_1 + \beta_2 DACF_2 + \beta_3 OUSData_3 + \beta_4 FDP_4 + \beta_5 PPRC_5 + \varepsilon_{it} \quad \text{eq. 2}$$

Where BI is the budget implementation, IGF is the internal generated fund been low when released, DACF, is district assembly common fund low when received, OUSData is outdated and unrealistic socio economic data, FPD is failure to prosecute defaulters, PPRC is the poor performance of revenue collectors, β_0 Indicate the constant parameter of the regression model. ($\beta_1 - \beta_5$) represent the coefficients of the independent variables on the dependent variable and ε_{it} is the stochastic or error term.

Dependent Variables

To test (Eq.1), factors affecting the budget preparation of MMDAs in Ghana, we measured budget preparation as respondent rating the likely of how these factors affect budget preparation of MMDAs in Ghana: delays in submission of inputs from other departments, inadequate funds to carry out the exercise unrealistic demands from department, outdated revenue data, and difficulty in budget preparation. Several scholars (Margaritis and Psillaki, 2010; Vithessonthi and Tongurai, 2015) have used this method as a measure in their studies. We test eq. 2, following prior studies such as (Margaritis and Psillaki, 2010; Vithessonthi and Tongurai, 2015 by measuring Budget implementation as respondent rating the influences of these factors: (Internal Generated Fund been low when released, district assembly common fund low when received, outdated and unrealistic socio economic data, failure to prosecute defaulters, and the poor performance of revenue collectors) affecting budget preparation.

Independent Variables

To examine the factors affecting budget preparation, the research used budget preparation challenges which are in line with the literature. (Adjei et al, 2012, Adu et al, 2016). They are on delays in submission of inputs from other departments, inadequate funds to carry out the exercise of unrealistic demands from department, outdated revenue data, and difficulty in budget preparation. They are signified by the effects they posed on MMDAs budget preparation in Ghana. This effect stems from budgeting and finance prior studies (Adjei et al, 2012, Adu et al, 2016). They will be measured as respondent perceptions will be asked about the factors affecting budget preparation of MMDAs with aid of Likert scale ranges from (1) strongly disagree to strongly agree (5).

Nonetheless, we measured the factors influencing the activities of budget implementation of MMDAs in Ghana using five influential factors which is consistent with the literature: Internal Generated Fund been low when released, district assembly common fund low when received, outdated and unrealistic socio economic data, failure to prosecute defaulters, and the poor performance of revenue collectors. Respondent perceptions will be asked about the factors affecting budget implementation on the usage of Likert scale choices from (1) strongly disagree to strongly agree (5).

Data Analysis

We processed the data obtained and analyzed using a statistical package for social science (SPSS). We maintained that, no pinpointing information data was obtained, and only summary results were reported. We used data from three selected Municipal, metropolitan district assembly of Ghana.

Table I Study Variables

We used Cronbach’s Alpha to test the reliability of study variables. From the table above, Cronbach's Alpha internal consistency threshold is 0.7, hence all the study variables are above the thresholds (>0.7).

Variable	Item	References	Cronbach’s Alpha
Budget preparation factors	Delays in submission of inputs from other departments	(Adjei et al, 2012, Adu et al, 2016).	0.77
	Inadequate funds to carry out the exercise unrealistic demands from department		0.757
	Outdated revenue data,		0.72
	Difficulty in budget preparation		0.723
Budget implementations challenges	Internal generated fund been low when released,	(Adjei et al, 2012, Adu et al, 2016).	0.812
	District assembly common fund low when received,		0.812
	Outdated and unrealistic socio economic data, Failure to prosecute defaulters,		0.74
	Poor performance of revenue collectors		8.7

Results and Findings

Table II Respondents Profile

Description		Percentages	Frequency
Position	District Coordinating Director	2.8	4
	District Internal Auditor	2.8	4
	District Budget Analyst	2.8	4
	Chief Finance Officer	2.8	4
	District accountants	2.8	4
	Assembly Member	82.8	116
	Revenue Superintendent	2.8	4
Gender	Male	92.8	130
		7.2	10
Age group	< 30 years	42.8	60
	31-40years	28.57	40
	41 and above years	28.57	40
Qualification			
	High school	7.14	10
	Higher National Diploma	35.7	50
	Bachelor's degree and above	50	70
	Certifications (ICA, ACCA, ICEM-UK)	7.14	10

From the results shown above, with the usage of 140 respondents, 16.8% (24) were district coordinating directors, district internal auditors, district budget analyst, chief finance officer, district accountants, and revenue superintendent. Most of the respondents were males with (130) representing 92.8 percent and the remaining were females. Interestingly, majority of the respondents were above the ages of (30) years. (42.9%, 60). Nonetheless, majority of the respondents hold bachelor's degree and above such as Master's degree, (7%, 10) have obtained professional certification such as ICA-Ghana, ACCA and other management and administration certificates.

Summary Statistics

We provide summary statistics of the variables utilized in the study. On average, MMDAs in Ghana's budgeting preparation is affected by 29%. It comes from an average of (13.2) emerging from a minimum and maximum of (13.9). The average of delays in submission of inputs from other departments is 45% with a minimum of (1) and maximum of (2). On average, 26% of MMDAs having inadequate funds to carry out the exercise of unrealistic demands from department. Moreover, outdated revenue posited 34%, and MMDAs finding it difficult to

prepare budget posited an average of (1.5). Practically, budget preparation in MMDAs in Ghana faced numerous obstacles.

Additionally, budget implementation has a minimum value of (4.3) and a maximum value of (4.4). The positive signs of both minimum and maximum values signifies the increasing challenges regarding budget implementation of MMDAs in Ghana. From the results, the average value of MMDAs faced with a challenges in implementing budget prepared is 47%. The mean value of MMDAs receiving a minimum amount of internal generated fund is 34 percent having minimum of (3.4) and a maximum of (4.6). Nonetheless, sampled MMDAs engulfed a challenged as a results of district assembly common fund (DACF) been low when released. It had a minimum and maximum value of (2.7), and (3.2) respectively. In fact, outdated and unrealistic socio economic data had a mean of (), failure to prosecute defaulters with an average percentage of (), and poor performance of revenue collectors with an average of (21%) having a minimum and maximum of (2.5, 3.5) respectively. The table below shows the summary of the summary statistics.

Table 3 Summary Statistics

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Maximum</i>	<i>Minimum</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>
BI	0.291	4.461	4.31	0.5591
BP	4.7	4.454	4.31	0.6551
DeIM	4.5	3.879	1.609	0.5175
ODRDT	3.4	3.581	1.527	0.5596
DFTY	1.5	3.631	2.713	0.5591
IGF	3.4	4.501	3.331	0.7592
DACF	3.1	2.711	3.221	0.5817
OUSDData	2.68	4.461	3.412	0.5562
FPD	3.19	3.354	2.355	0.6493
PPRC	2.112	3.551	2.531	0.4595

Empirical Results

We examined the factors and challenges affecting the Municipal, Metropolitan and District Assemblies in Ghana. We used multiple regression method to test the hypothesis stated, and the results are shown below. From model (1), with the regression model where no control variables were added. Based on the findings, we experienced negative relationship between budget preparation and the factor variables. We experience, departments dalliance in submitting inputs to the budget analyst had strongest negative effect on budget preparation with major magnitude. The findings are generally consistent with the hypothesis.

On the other hand, from table (4), we tested for the challenges affecting budget implementation of MMDAs in Ghana. From the results of the table, we established negative effect of the challenging factors on budget implementation. They are negatively related to budget implementation while failure to prosecute defaulters are positively related to budget implementation of MMDAs of Ghana. It is imperative to note that, the positive effect of failure to prosecute defaulters are not consistent with the hypothesis (6) but the rest are consistent with the literature. Therefore, the findings shows that, all the challenges variables are negatively affects budget implementation since the coefficient of factor variables are statistically significant.

Table 3 Correlation matrix results

	IB	DeIM	ODRDT	DFTY
IB	1			
DeIM	-0.4550*	1		
ODRDT	-0.2625*	-0.3193*	1	
DFTY	0.417	0.2165*	0.4031	1

	BP	DACF	IGF	OUTD	PPRC	FDP
BP	1					
IGF	-0.4771	1				
DACF	-0.2813	0.3061	1			
OUTD	-0.1814	0.4681	0.1523*	1		
PPRC	-0.3612	0.2551*	0.0874	0.3401	1	
FDP	0.3651	0.1061**	0.1921	0.4038	0.2871*	1

Table 5 Regression

Factor Variable	Coefficient	T-statistics	Std. Error	Sig. Value
DeIM	-4.14	-3.43	1.92	0.0001*
ODRDT	-3.37	-1.21	2.77	0.0002*
DFTY	-1.69	0.70	2.41	0.0301*

Challenges affecting budget implementation

The table below shows the results from the regression on the challenges affecting budget implementation of MMDAs in Ghana. From the findings, all the factor variables (Low IGF, DACF, outdated and unrealistic socio economic and poor performance of revenue collectors), used to examine the effects on budget implementation explains 68% as signified by the adjusted R-square of (0.68). This implies that, the challenging factors contributes to negative effects of MMDAs of 68 percent whiles other factors not considered in the study contributes to the remaining (32%).

Table 6

Factor Variable	Coefficient	T-statistics	Std. Error	Sig. Value
DACF	0.00794	0.00462	1.718	0.572**
OUTD	0.3189	0.0566	5.632	0.0000*

IGF	0.01272	0.0063	1.995	0.047*
PPRC	0.5423	0.0352	18.221	0.0000*
FDP	0.0174	-0.0106	-1.6334	0.1039*
<i>Note: *, **, *** shows 1%, 5%, and 10% of significant levels respectively.</i>				
Multiple R	R-Square	Adjusted R Square	Standard Error Estimate	
0.61	0.78	0.68	0.13	

Moreover, all the factor variables are statistically and significantly affect budget implementation and the tendency of MMDAs budget implementation with these challenges is sophisticated. The findings validates prior empirical results regarding challenges confronting MMDAs in Ghana. (Adu et al, 2000). Nonetheless, the results lengthen support institutional theory with the argument that, structures, rules, routines becomes established as authoritative guidelines for social behavior since institution is absolutely a function of an extent to which all consequential actors internalize the norms and social values required.

Conclusions, Summary and policy Recommendations

We examined the factors and challenges affecting budgeting of MMDAs in Ghana. Specifically, we assessed the factors affecting budget preparation and challenges affecting the budget implementation using 4 MMDAs in Ghana. We find negative relationship between budget preparation and the factor variables. This means that, all the factor variables (delays in submission of inputs from other departments, inadequate funds to carry out the exercise unrealistic demands from department, outdated revenue data, difficulty in budget preparation) are negatively related to budget preparation of MMDAs in Ghana. Interestingly, the effect is significant. The other important findings support the relationship between budget implementation and it challenging factors. We find a statistical significant negative effect of budget implementation and the challenging factors. We established that, all the discussed variable factors negatively affects budget implementation of MMDAs of Ghana. These findings are consistent in the literature of budgeting in Municipal assemblies. We established that, the IGF (IGFs) such as rates and fees, rents, fines and licenses, investments and income from commercial activities should be paid heed to because of capacity challenges in revenue mobilization, mismanagement and corruption. Management failure to prosecute defaulters is a strongest challenges confronting budget to be implemented. Additionally, even though the DACF was created as a constitutional requirement, based on the findings, there are instances where payments into the funds are delayed for more than year, resulting in the failure to disburse funds to the MMDAs. Therefore, government and all institutions involved should aid released DACF on time, and enough to meet and transform livelihood of the citizens in the Districts. We established that, approaching the aforementioned findings from budgeting and administrative perspective, all departments must update their data since providing unrealistic data warrant problems for budget implementation. In terms of practical implication,

There is a potential caveats of our study. We examined only 4 MMDAs which makes the sample small. Further studies could sample at least ten (10) MMDAs on this same subject. Additionally, we are calling for further studies to add other factors that were not considered in our study since we utilized cross sectional reported variables.

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Appendix: The selected Municipal, Metropolitan and District Assembly

Abbreviation	Name of the Organization
OFMA	Offinso Municipal Assembly
KMA	Kumasi Metropolitan Assembly
MMA	Mampong Municipal Assembly
SDA	Sekyere District Assembly